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The Morphology and Syntax of Adjectives in English and Pashto: A Contrastive Study

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Abstract

This study is an attempt to carry out a contrastive analysis of adjectives in Pashto and English, adopting a corpus-based approach to examine their morphological and syntactic properties. The study highlights the way Contrastive Analysis (CA) can be useful in understanding the uses of adjectives along different parameters in Pashto and English languages and facilitates the learning of English as a second language. The findings of the study show that adjectives show both similarities and differences in the target language (English) and in the source language (Pashto) and learners generally map their knowledge of adjectives in English on the basis of their morphology and syntax of Pashto adjectives. The study reveals that one of the causes of grammatical inaccuracies concerning the use of English adjectives among the Pashto native speakers is the interference of their first language (Pashto). This study addresses a key concern for Pashto-speaking learners interested in learning English worldwide. The Contrastive Analysis of English and Pashto provides a foundation for designing more effective language learning strategies. Moreover, this analysis can also help in predicting potential obstacles a learner may possibly face in the learning of English as a second language .

Keywords: Linguistic Interference, Contrastive Analysis of Pashto and English, Syntactic Structure, Morphological Changes, Cross-linguistic Comparison

1. Introduction

Every individual possesses an inherent capacity to acquire his initial language. This process is often referred to first language acquisition, which encompasses terms like mother language, primary language, or native language (Sinha et al., 2009). Mother tongue is the first language a child learns in his formative years. Conversely, the second language pertains to a language that is not inherently person's own but is acquired for professional, educational, official, or societal purposes. Students learning English language often face challenges in achieving mastery. During their learning journey, they frequently encounter errors in both spoken and written forms. These difficulties are rooted in the contrasting systems of their native tongue and second language. (Ameri et al., 2010). When a learner consciously starts the process of learning a new language, the linguistic patterns of already acquired language, i.e. first or native language of the learner, impels the learner to make a new linguistic pattern of the target language in order to match it with the native language. This phenomenon is known as language interference. Language

interference is also called language transfer or linguistic interference. Dulay (1982) describes interference as an automatic transfer of knowledge about the surface structure of the first language onto the surface of the second language. Besides this, Ellis (1997) recognizes interference as 'transfer', and contends that "the influence that the learner's L1 exerts over the acquisition of an L2" (p.51) .

Linguistic interference can be in negative or positive manner. When the knowledge or understanding of first language hinders and obstructs to learn or understand the second language, it is called negative interference. Alternatively, there can be positive linguistic interference. It happens when knowledge of first language promotes the learning of the second language. These negative or positive effects can be on any aspect of language: vocabulary, grammar, accent, spelling, sentence structure and so on (Lott, 1983) .

1.1. Adjectives vs. Determiners

An adjective is defined as a term that alters or qualifies a noun or pronoun in three primary ways: positively (e.g., small, wonderful), comparatively (e.g., smaller, more wonderful), or superlatively (e.g., smallest, most wonderful). Its role is to offer additional details about the definition of a noun or pronoun by functioning as a modifier. Within the conventional English eight parts of speech, adjectives hold a significant place; however, contemporary linguistics make a distinction between adjectives and other words like determiners, previously categorized as adjectives. Semantically, the central purpose of an adjective is to impart a distinct quality to a noun or pronoun, setting it apart from others. Demonstratives, articles and indefinites are conventionally categorized as adjectives. This distinction is both syntactic and morphosyntactic. Demonstratives like "that" and "these" canonically take determinate position in NPs such as "this house" or "these houses." They, however, can also feature as subjects—a quality that set them apart from adjectives. Consider example .(1)

1. This is the house I bought in 1960.

Similarly, "that" as a determiner selects a single NP while "these" a plural. This morphosyntactic property is not obvious in adjectives: "a big house/ big houses". Thus, words enhancing the subject are denoted as adjectives. These words serve to modify or augment the meaning of a noun or pronoun. For instance, in the phrase "lazy girl," the adjective "lazy" characterizes the nature of the noun "girl." This description helps ascertain what kind of girl she is – the answer being "lazy." Likewise, in (2), an answer to the question "Who among the boys was punished?" the response pertains to the one with negative behavior. Here, the adjective "bad" is applied to convey this attribute (Amer et al., 2012).

2. The bad boy was punished .

English as a Second Language (ESL) refers to the learning of English by people whose native language is different. This often involves acquiring skills in speaking, listening, reading, and writing English. English as a second language in Pakistan has a complex history and status. Pakistani students generally have positive attitudes towards learning English, primarily for educational reasons, while retaining a strong connection to their native languages (Khalid, 2016). Similarly, in Pakistan, English language learning and teaching is an essential component of the educational system. However, English language learners in Pakistan make various errors in both spoken and written forms, which , according to (Brown, 2000), is a common occurrence among English language learners. One of the reasons for these errors could be interference from the learners' native language, which led to the development of the Contrastive Analysis hypothesis in the 20th century. Contrastive Analysis is a linguistic theory that focuses on comparing and contrasting two or more languages to identify similarities and differences between their linguistic structures. It was developed in the mid-20th century to predict and explain errors that learners

of a second language might make based on the differences between their native language and the target language .

The current study undertakes a comparative analysis of adjectives in English and Pashto. The study is a definite, yet not a conclusive attempt to make a comparative and contrastive analyses of adjectives in English and Pashto languages. The Introduction sections provides an account of this goal. In the next section titled Literature Review, a background of research done on Pashto has been undertaken. Section 3 rationalizes the theoretical framework and states that Contrastive Analysis serves as a valuable tool in understanding the complexities of adjectival usage in these languages and the potential implications for the effective learning of English as a second language. Section 4 presents an analysis of the research topic. In addition, it is an attempt to investigate the syntactic peculiarities of adjectives in the cited languages. It also highlights the influence of the native language on the process of acquiring English as a second language. Section 5 is the Conclusion of the paper. It contains a summary of the findings and signifies the importance of findings by uncovering potential errors made by Pashto-native learners of English when handling adjectives .

Research Question

The study is designed to provide working answers to the following research questions :

- i. What possible syntactic configurations between English and Pashto adjectives are analyzable within the framework of Contrastive Analysis?
- ii. How do Pashto learners map their knowledge of English adjectives on the basis of adjectives in Pashto language ?

1.4 The Significance of the Study

There is no denying the fact that the world-wide use and currency of English language has led to an ever-increasing demand for its systemic analysis. The researchers believe that the present study will respond to one of the leading concerns of Pashto speaking people regarding their learning of English language in general and adjectives in particular. In other words, the present research is a is an attempt to architect their viable errors in learning adjectives and potential recommendations for overcoming these errors .

2. Literature Review

Syntactic research on Pashto language is characteristically scanty. Likewise, a systematic analysis of adjectives in Pashto is under explored. Scholarly research, however, has been undertaken in Pashto and other languages .

An insightful study by Naeem and Khan (2016) delves into the derivational process of Pashto nouns from adjectives. The study explores how adjectives transform into nouns and highlights the intricate morphological changes in Pashto. This research significantly contributes to the understanding and refinement of word classes, particularly within the context of parts of speech in Pashto language. Similarly, Mahjour, (2019) explores the parallels and divergences between Pashto and Dari adjectives. The comparative nature of the study makes a thorough comparison of adjectives in both languages, accentuating their shared traits and distinctive features. The investigation made valuable contributions to the grammatical understanding of both languages, furnishing researchers and learners with insightful perspectives. In a separate study focusing on adjective placement within English/Spanish mixed determiner sentences, Nicolus and López (2022) venture into the realm of noun-adjective order within code-switched determiner phrases. They systematically define the concept of order and inquire into the homogeneity of adjective classes. Through an experiment involving around 30 English/Spanish bilingual speakers, they employ code-switching to signal the determining element for adjective order in determiner

phrases. The experiment yields diverse outcomes, yet the researchers concludes that the noun predominantly governs the word sequence in a determiner phrase (De Nicolás et al., 2022) . Similarly, Pettibone, Leroux, and Klassen (2021) conducted a study on adjective placement in indigenous and non-indigenous Spanish. They attempt to examine the intuition of native and non-native Spanish speakers regarding the interpretation of adjective order in prenominal and post-nominal positions. They also ask L2 learners about their intuitions on adjective order. The study involves a large number of participants, and the results shows that many native and non-native Spanish speakers accept the post-nominal order of adjectives .

3. Research Methodology

The study is characterized as comparative as the researchers examine the usage of adjectives in both Pashto and English languages. The researchers have used a corpus of both languages to make this comparative and Contrastive Analysis. Data was verified from 20 native speakers of Pashto language. A set of sentences/phrases is employed by the researcher to draw comparisons between various categories of adjectives employed in Pashto and English. By identifying the structural differences (comparison of adjectives/noun phrases) between the native language and the target language, Contrastive Analysis attempts to predict potential challenges for learners. This information can be used to design language teaching materials and strategies that can address these potential pitfalls.

4. Theoretical Framework

Fisiak (1981) defines Contrastive Linguistics as a branch of linguistics that concentrates on juxtaposing two or more languages or language subsystems to uncover shared characteristics and distinctions among them. It further asserts that Contrastive Analysis is an integral component of second language learning models, as it anticipates that speakers of a given native language will likely commit grammatical errors when constructing sentences in a second language. These errors are expected to resemble those present in their native language structure. (Fisiak, 1981). The inception of contrastive linguistics can be attributed to American linguist C.C. Fries in 1945, further developed by Robert Lado (1957) in his work "Linguistics Across Cultures." Advocates of Contrastive Analysis contends that by scrutinizing language resemblances and differences, the process of teaching these languages to learners will be aided . An American linguist Fries (1952) claims that contrastive linguistics compares the relationship between target and native language by using the effective materials which are rooted in scientific description. Furthermore, Bloomfield (quoted in Smith, 1991) lends support to the fundamental concept of the linguistic model associated with the Contrastive Analysis hypothesis. This idea finds further illumination in the works of Fries (Fries, 1952) and Lado (Lado, 1957). They propose that the psychological foundation of the Contrastive Analysis hypothesis is linked to (S-R) Stimulus-Response theory. Central to this theory is the notion of interference and transfer between a person's native language and their second language. Lado (1957), for example, contends that learners tend to transfer various aspects of their native language onto the second language they are acquiring. This transfer is analogous to how individuals carry elements of one culture into another. Fisiak (1981) defines Contrastive Analysis or contrastive linguistics as a subset of linguistics primarily concerned with comparing two or more languages or language subsystems. The goal of contrastive linguistics is to comparatively analyze different languages to identify both similarities and differences. Therefore, Contrastive Analysis serves as a tool to identify obstacles and challenges in the process of learning a new language .

5. Findings and Discussion

After a thorough theoretical analysis of the languages under investigation, the study comes up with the following findings .

5.1 The Syntax of Adjectives in Pashto and English

In language structure, each language adheres to a specific word order. The difference in word order not only effects fundamental sentence structure but also determines the placement of modifiers, adjectives, and adverbs. While English typically positions these elements before noun or verb, Pashto, with its SOV structure, arranges them in a manner that differs from English. The placement and order of adjectives in a sentence is an important aspect of grammar in both English and Pashto. Adjectives describe the qualities, characteristics, or attributes of nominals and pronominals (collectively called NPs [noun phrase]) and provide additional information about them. The order in which adjectives appear before a noun is generally consistent, although there might be some flexibility based on style and context.

Adjective stacking, also known as cumulative adjectives or coordinate adjectives, is the practice of using multiple adjectives to describe a noun at the same time. As a matter of fact, adjectives are used in sentence structure of both English and Pashto. English adjectives follow a more rigid order compared to Pashto language, which is characterized by a greater degree of flexibility in adjective placement than English. When more than one adjective occurs before a noun in English, they are normally placed in a certain order. The order of adjectives in English is in the following order: Opinion, Size, Age, Shape, Color, Origin, Material and Purpose/kind. If the recommended order is violated, the sentences seem odd. On the other hand, the order of adjectives in Pashto can be reshuffled and the sentence doesn't seem odd. Consider the following NPs .

1. "A fast Italian sports car" (He was thrilled to witness the roar of a fast Italian sports car.)
(1)is an acceptable structure (as it conforms to the recommended order of adjectives i.e. opinion -origin-purpose/kind)
2. "An Italian fast sports car" (He was thrilled to witness the roar of an Italian fast sports car)
(2)is an unacceptable structure (origin is followed by opinion)

Now consider the following NPs in Pashto given in the table below .

Example	Pashto	English
3	يوه ښکلې دنگه جنې	a beautiful tall girl
	سارا يوه ښکلې دنگه جنې ده	Sarah is a beautiful tall girl
4	يوه دنگه ښکلې جنې	a tall beautiful girl
	سارا يوه دنگه ښکلې جنې ده	Sarah is a tall beautiful girl

In example 3 opinion is followed by size and in example 4 size is followed by opinion. Both structures are admissible in Pashto language.

5.2 Predicative and Attributive Adjectives

Predicative and attributive adjectives are terms used to describe the positions of adjectives in relation to the nouns they modify. Attributive adjectives are prenominal in nature. They provide additional information about the NPs. It can be in postnominal position but prenominal position is more common in English. Predicative adjectives are adjectives that are commonly used postnominally. They usually appear after linking verbs such as "to be", "to seem", "to look", "to appear", "to become", "to feel", "to remain" etc. to describe the subject of the sentence. Adjectives are recognized as attributive and predicative in prenominal and postnominal position. However, there's a distinction in the placement (prenominal and postnominal positions) of predicative adjectives in English and Pashto. When adjectives are used predictively, differs between the two languages. In Pashto sentences, a predicative adjective is invariably positioned beside near the noun it describes. Following are the examples.

S. No	Pashto	English
1	آم خور دی	English version: mango sweet is

		Cf ¹ . The mango is sweet.
2	جنی بښکلې ده	English version: girl beautiful is. Cf. The girl is beautiful.
3	جنی بښکلې بښکاری	English version: girl beautiful seems. Cf. The girl seems beautiful.

Observe the difference between “آم خور دی” here خور is postnominal” and “آم خور” is prenominal. Pashto has both prenominal and postnominal adjectives or the same adjective can be recognized as both. One important syntactic difference is that a postnominal adjective does not occupy the same position as in English because, unlike English, Pashto does not have the same syntax. It is SOV language. Hence here S consists of NP and VP and VP consists of NP +V (see tree diagram (ii.) on the other hand, English is SVO and here VP consists of V +NP (see (i.)

In English, predicative adjectives are often used with a linking verb (such as "is," "are," "was," "were," etc.), which connects the subject with the adjective. This linking verb serves as a bridge, allowing the adjective to describe the subject's state or attribute. On the other hand, the placement of predicative adjectives in Pashto is unique. Unlike English, there is no requirement for a linking verb between the adjective and the noun it modifies. Instead, the adjective is positioned directly adjacent to the noun it qualifies. This immediate adjacency creates a seamless connection between the adjective's description and the noun, eliminating the need for an intervening linking verb. In other words, English employs linking verbs to associate predicative adjectives with subjects, whereas Pashto places predicative adjectives directly next to the nouns they describe.

When it comes to attributive adjectives, both English and Pashto exhibit a shared pattern. In both languages, attributive adjectives serve the purpose of directly modifying nouns and are positioned before the nouns. This common structure enables speakers to effectively communicate qualities or characteristics associated with the nouns. As a result, the placement of attributive adjectives stands as a notable similarity in the linguistic expression of both languages. Following are the example.

S. No	Pashto	English
1	سارا یوه بښکلې جنی ده	Sara is a beautiful girl
2	ما یو خور آم اوخورو	I ate a sweet mango

¹ Cf. stands for correct form.

Consider (iii) .

iii. Sara is beautiful (postnominal) سارا ښکلې ده

In both cases (۵د), which is a copula (corresponding to English “is”) is recognized in the end position. This shows that the prenominal or postnominal usage is structure dependent. In English, S is followed by V (is) and then AP (beautiful). In Pashto, S is followed by AP (beautiful) and then V .(۵د)

Similarly, tree diagram of example (2) in the table above further illustrates the concept.

5.3 Morphological Changes in Pashto Adjectives

Morphology is a fundamental aspect of every language including Pashto. Variations in morphological structure exist between languages and their individual elements. In Pashto, adjectives are morphologically marked for the gender of the noun they modify. In other words, same adjective has different masculine and feminine forms. This morphological adaptation reflects the inherent gender distinctions within Pashto adjectives. To clarify the concept, consider the following examples:

S. No	Pashto	English
1	غټه ښځه	Fat woman
2	غټ سړی	Fat man
3	هوبښیار هلک	Intelligent boy
4	هوبښیاره جنی	Intelligent girl
5	خوړم	Sweet mango
6	خواره الوچه	Sweet plum

Pashto phrases provided above exemplify a consistent pattern of noun-adjective agreement, where the gender of the noun actuate changes in adjective form. This process is evident in the above examples. In the first two phrases, the adjectives "غټ" (fat) modifies the masculine noun "سړی" (man), while "غټه" is used for the feminine noun ښځه (woman). Likewise, in phrases 3 and 4, the adjective "هوبښیار" is employed. In phrase 3, it precedes the masculine noun "هلک" (boy) as "هوبښیار هلک" (intelligent boy) In contrast, in phrase 4, the same adjective "هوبښیار" takes the form "هوبښیاره" to match the feminine noun "جنی" (girl), resulting in "هوبښیاره جنی" (intelligent girl). This consistent adjustment of adjectives based on the gender of the noun highlights a fundamental aspect of Pashto grammar, it reflects how the language exhibits gender-specific agreement in adjective usage. These examples also illustrate that Pashto is a highly genderized language. Whereas in English animate and more particularly human nominals are genderized, Pashto assigns gender to both animate and inanimate nouns. This genderization, however, is realized with the help of adjectives. As can be seen above in example 5 and 6, an animate like noun “mango” is assigned a masculine gender with an adjective “خوړم” while the noun “plum” is marked as feminine and this genderization is realized with the adjective “خواره”

This phenomenon also indicates that, unlike English, the morphology of Pashto adjectives is gender oriented. This is yet another parametric variation between the two languages under investigation. Pashto adjectives also have number property. As an illustration, consider the following examples:

S. No	Pashto	English
1	هغه زما خور ملگری دی	He is my sweet friend
2	دوی زما خواږه ملگری دي	They are my sweet friends

As examples (1) and (2) show, with a singular NP “ملگری” (friend) the adjective is marked singular. However, once the nominal is pluralized as “ملگری” (friends), the adjective undergoes a morphological change and assumes a plural form “خواږه” in Pashto.

5.4 Degree of Adjectives in Pashto and English

In English, you can create the comparative degree of an adjective by inflectional method or by analytical method. In the former, the suffix “-er” is added to the base form of the adjective to make a comparative adjective. The superlative degree is formed with the addition of “-est.” (Leech et al., 2013; Quirk et al., 1973). In the latter, periphrastic markers “more” and “most” are placed before the comparative and superlative degrees respectively. In Pashto, the comparative and superlative degrees are marked with syntactic markers ’د’ and ’نه’ as shown in the examples below

Pashto	English
داحمد نه ورکوتی	younger than Ahmad
د ټولو نه لوړه لک	The tallest boy

The following examples illustrate the morphology and syntax of the degrees of Pashto adjectives.

S.No	Pashto	English
3.	آم د الوچه نه خور وی	Mango than plum sweet is. Cf. A mango is sweeter than plum.
4.	احمد د اجمل نه ډیر قابل دی	Ahmad than Ajmal more intelligent is. Cf. Ahmad is more intelligent than Ajmal.
5.	احمد ورکوتی دی	Ahmad is young.
6.	احمد داجمل نه ورکوتی دی	Ahmad is younger than Ajmal.
7.	احمد جماعت کي د ټولو نه ورکوتی دی	Ahmad the class among all youngest is. Cf. Ahmad is the youngest among all in the class.
8.	احمد د ټولو نه ورکوتی دی	Ahmad is the youngest among all.

It is clear from the above examples that Pashto doesn’t use the suffix –er to make the comparative degree of short adjectives. Long adjectives, on the other hand, are formed with periphrastic marker “ډیر” as can be seen in example 4 above. Now examine examples 5, 6, 7, and 8. These examples indicate that in Pashto the positive (absolute), comparative and superlative form of the adjective does not undergo any morphological change.

5.5 Possessive Determiners in English and Pashto

Both English and Pashto languages employ possessive determiners, and their usage is remarkably similar in both linguistic systems. In English, the possessive forms of determiners used for the first person remain unaffected by number and gender. It reflects that possessive determiners forms remain consistent with both singular and plural nouns.

S.no	Pashto	English
1.	زما گاږی رارا وان دی	My car coming is. Cf. My car is coming.
2.	زما گاږي رارا وان دي	My cars coming are. Cf. My cars are coming.

These examples show that a singular NP with a singular possessive selects “دی” whereas a plural NP with a plural possessive selects “دي”. This selection of auxiliaries “دی” and “دي” mark the first possessive singular and the second plural.

Now consider the past forms of the verbs.

S.no	Pashto	English
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1.	زما گاړې روراسيدو	My car arrived.
2.	زما گاړې روراسيدل	My cars arrived.

The morphology of the verb changes with change in the number of the noun. In example 1, verb is marked for a singular noun while in example 2, verb is used for plural nouns. These examples lead us to this tentative conclusion that possessive "زما" is both singular and plural in Pashto. It corresponds to definite article in English which can take both singular and plural nouns. For instance,

- a. The house
- b. The houses

Likewise, consider the following examples.

S.no	Pashto	English
1.	زمونږ گاړې راغئ	Our car arrived.
2.	زمونږ گاړې راغلل	Our cars arrived.

The verb "راغلل" is clearly marked for plural subject. This means that the NP "زمونږ گاړې" has plural determiner (D) followed by a plural head "گاړې". The conclusion of the discussion is that possessives like "زمونږ, ستاسو" are both singular and plural in Pashto.

However, when it comes to the usage of possessive determiners in the second person, there exists a divergence between English and Pashto. In English, possessive forms remain unaltered in relation to number. Conversely, in Pashto, the forms of possessive adjectives undergo modifications based on number as exemplified below.

S.no	Pashto	English
1.	ستا گاړې راراوان دی	Your car coming is. Cf. Your car is coming.
2.	ستاسو گاړې راراوان دي	Your cars coming are. Cf. Your cars are coming.

ستا is both singular and plural in Pashto. ستا is its informal variant used as a singular. Example 2 shows that the verb is inflected for plural second person in Pashto. This evidence suggests the same principle as mentioned above that possessives are morphologically unmarked yet inflectionally marked for singular and plural forms in Pashto.

A prominent contrast arises while considering the use of possessive adjectives in the third person case. In English, singular "his/her" form is used for both singular and plural nouns, while a distinct plural form "their" is introduced. However, in Pashto language, a distinctive approach is taken. In Pashto, a demonstrative pronoun "دا" is assimilated before the possessive adjective in the third person case, irrespective of whether the noun is singular or plural. Moreover, akin to English "his/her," Pashto also incorporates separate masculine and feminine forms. Following are the examples.

S.no	Pashto	English
1.	د احمد گاړې دا بس سره وچنگيدو	The car of Ahmad the bus hit. ² Cf. Ahmad's car hit the bus.

When the nominal "Ahmad" is pronominalized

S.no	Pashto	English
2.	د هغه گاړې دا بس سره وچنگيدو	His car the bus hit. Cf. His car hit the bus.

Examples 1 and 2 show that the demonstrative (دا) is used with both nominal and pronominal possessive structures. When both examples 1 and 2 are compared with their corresponding

² English employs inflected genitive for human possessors. Pashto, on the contrary, canonically uses periphrastic genitive (of-construction) for possessors. The use of inflectional marker ډ validates this analysis.

English versions, we observe that English possessives have determiner “the” in nominal and pronominal structures. Hence for Pashto we can have the following projection rule :

i. NP → D1 + D2 + N

Where D1 is demonstrative (د) and D2 is possessive (د احمد/ هغه). D2 can be either a nominal or a pronominal.

Similarly ,

1. دا هغه گاړی راغلی

2. دا هغه گاړی راغلل

For English the projection rule as stated in PSRs (Chomsky, 1965):

NP → (D⁺) N

When (D) in (ii) is a N then

a. Ahmad’s car

When it is a pronominal then

b. His car

But (c) is not possible .

c. *The Ahmad’s car

The unacceptability of (c) is attributed to the complementary distribution of determiners as stated in Abney’s DP hypothesis.³

The conclusion of the discussion is that Pashto disregards DP hypothesis in pronominal possessive structures. This can clearly be seen in the addition of more than one determiner as given in (i).

S.no	Pashto	English
3.	دهغوی گاړی راغی	Her car arrived.
4.	دهغوی کور غټ دی	Their house is big.
5.	دهغوی کورونه غټ دي	Their houses are big.
6.	دهغوی گاړی راغلل	Her cars arrived.
7.	دا هغوی گاړی راوورسیدو	Their car arrived.
8.	دا هغوی گاړی راوورسیدل	Their cars arrived.
9.	دا هغوی گاړی غټ دي	Their car is big.
10.	دهغوی گاړی غټ دي	Their cars are big.

The verb “راغی” the past form, marks the subject “دهغوی گاړی” singular. This means that the possessive “دهغوی” is a singular possessive determiner in (3). On the other hand, the verb in (5) indicates the plural form of the possessive determiner. On the basis of these examples, we can say that the possessive determiner “دهغوی” which marks the NP feminine is both singular and plural in Pashto. The same conclusion can be derived about the masculine. “دا هغه” In the sentence دی دهغوی کور غټ دی, corresponds to the singular copula “is” in (4). Similarly “دي”, is the plural form of “be” that corresponds to “are” in English. These examples show that, like English, subject in Pashto agrees with the copula that serves as a complement. Likewise, examples (8) and (9) illustrate that verbs in Pashto are not marked for third person plural “دا هغوی” However, we can test the validity of this assumption in case of copula. Examples 9 and 10 show that the copula “دی” and “دي” agree with the subject of the sentences “دي”. which is the plural form used with the plural subject indicates that the possessive determiner “دهغوی” must be taken plural keeping in view with DP hypothesis.

5.6 Errors in the Use of Adjectives

³ Steven Abney’s seminal dissertation (Abney, 1987) in which he proposed that it is actually the determiner that heads the noun phrase

Following are the sentences of students who are learning English as a second language. These sentences have grammatical errors, inappropriate word choices, or missing articles/prepositions because of the influence native language (Pashto). The mistakes in these sentences might stem from the influence of Pashto as it reflects the patterns of Pashto language.⁴

S.no	Pashto	English
1	هغه يو تکړه رنگ ساز دی هغه يو تکړه رنگ سازه دی	He is a brilliant painter. She is a brilliant *paintress.
2	کاري رو دی د خراب چلی	The car is slow. *She runs awkwardly.
3	زما پلار ماته ډالی راکړه دا زما د ژوند د ټولو نه خوشحاله ورځ ده	My father gave me a present. It is the *most happiest day of my life.
4	د يو ډير څه سکول دی	This is *a best school.
5	هغه د هغه نه غوره ده	She is superior *than him
6	علي ډير هوشيار دی که زه؟	Ali is more intelligent *or I
7	دا يو ډير اسان حل دی	This is *an easier solution

From the above mentioned examples, it is clear that the corresponding form in Pashto shows that it is because of influence of first language interference. In example 1, the error occurs because of common gender of noun. In Pashto, it has both masculine and feminine forms. Likewise, in example 2, "car" has neutral gender in English. On the other hand, it is handled as feminine noun in Pashto. In the same way in other examples, double superlatives and literal translations make the sentences faulty. 3500, 3500, 3500

6. Conclusion

The study does not only highlight the linguistic similarities and differences but also identify errors that arise from the distinct usage patterns in each language, particularly affecting Pashto speakers learning English. Notably, while basic predicative and attributive adjectives are used similarly across both languages, differences emerge in the use and morphological construction of adjective degrees which lead to common errors. It also explored how well Contrastive Analysis predictions aligned with real-world results. While basic adjectives are similar in both languages, complexities arise in describing degrees of adjectives. English language learners encounter hurdles due to interference of their first language. The study confirms that Contrastive Analysis remains relevant for language learning, especially in KPK. The study validates the linguistic value of Contrastive Analysis in illuminating tricky patterns and structures within adjective usage. Likewise, Contrastive Analysis is constructive in guiding language instructors and teachers on how to address specific challenges faced by learners from distinct language backgrounds. This approach offers insights for effective language acquisition and instruction. The outcomes and procedures of the study can be constrained by various limitations, such as time, accessibility and resources. Consequently, the study's generalizations may be limited. It is worth noting that this research exclusively focuses on syntactic analysis of Pashto and English adjectives. Therefore, more research and digging are required to see the hidden insights of English and Pashto language .

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⁴ These sentences were collected from students studying in a government school in Peshawar KPK

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